

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

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Abstract. This article provides an excursion into the methods of teaching English. Throughout human history, many different educational methods have been developed. The article discusses the main ones, indicating their advantages and disadvantages.

Keywords: English language, method, teaching, technology, education.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, when the educational technology market is replete with proposals for a wide variety of methods for learning English, the question “What method do you use to teach?” is becoming more and more relevant, which indicates an increase in the culture of consumption of intellectual products.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Language teaching has acquired an applied character, whereas previously it was relatively abstract and theoretical. Aristotle also came up with the famous triad of teaching ethics, which corresponds perfectly with modern requirements: logos - quality of presentation, pathos - contact with the audience, ethos - attitude towards others. This rule is true for a speaker, an actor, and a foreign language teacher, whose role also involves the first two hypostases. The functions of a teacher in the educational process have changed significantly. A teacher-mentor, a teacher-dictator is not able to provide students with freedom of choice and provide the necessary freedom of study in comprehending such a subtle matter as language. Therefore, such a negative pedagogical image is gradually becoming part of history. He was replaced by a teacher-observer, a teacher-mediator, a teacher-pacifier and a leader. Although the personality of the teacher in this case fades into the background, its

influence on the audience, which, in turn, becomes more intimate, does not decrease, but on the contrary, increases. It is the teacher in most modern Russian and foreign courses who is the organizer of group interaction (the ideal team for learning a foreign language is currently considered a group of 10–15 people, since this is the number of people who can communicate with each other with maximum effect, interest and benefit).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fundamental technique

This is truly the oldest and most traditional technique. This is exactly how the lyceum students learned Latin and Greek, while French was absorbed naturally, along with strict suggestions from governesses and communication with maman and papan. The classical method, like no other, fits the description of the “plan to capture a fortress”: a phonetics code, visual images of syntactic structures, mandatory vocabulary [1]. The student clearly understands: in order to become known as Sir Calm, Monsieur Gallantry or Herr Sanity: a) is ready to spend 2–3 years; b) be patient (learning begins with the basics); c) must remember how the subject, object and object can be expressed in “native, great and mighty” and what it is all about - syntax.

Classic approach to learning a foreign language

In connection with the above, the classical approach to learning a foreign language has also been somewhat transformed, but the unshakable principles of the “classics” of domestic language methods have been preserved. Sometimes they are actively used in schools of other methodological directions. The classical course is aimed at students of different ages and most often involves learning the language from scratch. The teacher’s tasks include traditional but important aspects of pronunciation, the formation of a grammatical base, and the elimination of psychological and language barriers that impede communication. The classics have not changed their goals, but the methods are different due to the new approach [2].

Linguistic and sociocultural method

One of the most serious and comprehensive methods of learning a foreign language is linguo-sociocultural, which involves an appeal to such a component as the social and cultural environment. Proponents of this method firmly believe that a language loses life when teachers and students set the goal of mastering only “lifeless” lexical and grammatical forms. Someone noted that personality is a product of culture. This definition also applies to language.

Communicative approach

The first line in the ranking of the popularity of methods is actively held by the communicative approach, which, as its name implies, is aimed at the practice of communication. This technique works great in Europe and the USA.

The communicative technique, as its name suggests, is aimed specifically at the possibility of communication. Of the four “pillars” on which any language training rests (reading, writing, speaking and listening comprehension), increased attention is paid to the last two. You will not hear particularly complex syntactic structures or serious vocabulary in class [3].

Intensive technique

The intensive method of teaching English is becoming especially popular. It helps out everyone for whom the phrases “Time is money” and “Money is time” are equivalent. A high degree of stereotypes allows you to study English at an intensive pace - this language consists of 25% clichés. By memorizing and practicing a certain range of “stable expressions”, you will, in principle, be able to explain yourself and understand your interlocutor. Of course, those who choose the intensive course will not be able to enjoy reading Byron in the original, but the goals of this course are completely different. The intensive method is aimed at developing “expressive speech behavior”, so it is often of a linguistic nature. Good courses will most likely provide you with the opportunity to communicate unlimitedly and maximize your potential, and the course will focus on your needs. Each student will be able to feel like an individual, and the teaching methods will most likely be dialogic communication and training [4].

CONCLUSION

So, on the domestic methodological market there are products for every taste. All that remains is to decide on the goals, means, and most importantly, the methods. Then choosing courses and training programs will not be so difficult.

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